

SIMCor

In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices

Call: H2020-SC1-DTH-2018-2020 (*Digital transformation in Health and Care*)

Topic: SC1-DTH-06-2020 (*Accelerating the uptake of computer simulations for testing medicines and medical devices*)

Grant agreement No: 101017578

Deliverable 2.6

Regulatory feedback report (2)

Due date of delivery: 30 April 2024

Actual submission date: 30 April 2024

Start of the project: 1 January 2021

End date: 31 June 2024

Reference

Name	SIMCor_D2.6_Regulatory feedback report (2)_VPH_30-04-2024
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Dissemination level	Public
Type	Report
Official delivery date	30 April 2024
Date of validation by the WP Leader	29 April 2024
Signature of the Coordinator	

Version log

Issue date	Version	Involved	Comments
01/07/2023	1.0	Raphaëlle Lesage Jan Brüning, Anna Rizzo, Liesbet Geris	First draft by VPH
20/07/2023	2.0	Raphaëlle Lesage, Liesbet Geris	Draft after RAB II meeting
30/03/2024	3.0	Janaki Raman Rangarajan,, Liesbet Geris	Revised with updates from RAB III – March 2024 meeting
23/04/2024	4.0	Janaki Raman Rangarajan, Liesbet Geris	Restructured layout and synthesis of RAB III discussions
26/04/2024	5.0	Jan Brüning, Anna Rizzo	Internal review by CHA and LYN
29/04/2024	6.0	Rene Bombien, Brent Craven	Approval by RAB advisors
30/04/2024	Final	Janaki Raman Rangarajan, Jan Brüning, Anna Rizzo	Final submitted version

Executive summary

This deliverable reports the interactions of the consortium with regulatory stakeholders in M20-M39 of the project. Those interactions were facilitated via a dedicated SIMCor *Regulatory Advisory Board* (RAB), and conferences, workshops, and one-to-one meetings with regulators, standardisation bodies and the in-silico community at large via the VPH. The outcomes of the discussions are reported here, and conclusions are derived for future actions and directions.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
ASME	American Society of Mechanical Engineers
BIO	Biotronik
CDRH	Centre for Devices and Radiological Health
CHA	Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin
CM&S	Computational Modelling & simulation
COU	Context of Use
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
GSP	Good Simulation Practice
HPC	High Performance Computing
IHS	Institut für Höhere Studien – Institute for Advanced Studies
IIB	Institut für Implantattechnologie und Biomaterialien e.V.
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
LYN	Lynkeus
MDCG	Medical Devices Coordination Group
M&S	Modelling & simulation
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
MDDT	Medical Device Development Tools
NB	Notified Body
NBR	Notified Body Representative
PHI	Philips Electronics Netherlands B.V.
RAB	Regulatory Advisory Board
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
SSCP	Summary of safety and clinical performance
TUE	Technische Universitt Eindhoven
TUG	Technical University Graz
UCL	University College of London
UTBV	Universitatea Transilvania Din Braşov
VC	Virtual Cohort
VPH	Virtual Physiological Human Institute

Introduction

Among the strategic objectives of SIMCor, Objective 1 is to develop standard protocols and validation workflows that will help integrate computer modelling solutions into the regulatory approval process, while Objective 4 is to accelerate the adoption and integration of computer simulations in the regulatory evaluation of medical devices through dissemination of results, increasing trust of users and community building. Hence, regular and in-depth interactions with regulatory authorities are needed to achieve those objectives.

The Task 2.3 of SIMCor is devoted to liaising with regulatory authorities in the healthcare sector, particularly regarding the design, development, piloting, clinical validation, and benchmarking of medical devices. This activity is carried out leveraging the contacts of VPH with EMA and the Memorandum of Understanding between the Avicenna Alliance and the *Food and Drug Administration* (FDA) - working on Good Simulation Practices -, as well as contacts with *notified bodies* (NB) and the in-silico medicine community at large. **SIMCor seeks to involve authorities in the development of *standard operating procedures* (SOPs) and the conduction of iterative feedback cycles regarding the design of *virtual cohort* (VC) generation, device effect simulation model validation and translation into the clinical setting.** The plan is to discuss, agree and introduce recommendations and guidelines throughout the project implementation, with round ups at regular project milestones.

The scope of the regulatory liaison within SIMCor is to open up the dialogue with regulatory authorities and identify **a path in which the type of in-silico approach we propose could be used in regulatory submissions for medical device approval.** Through this process, SIMCor aims to advance the field of *computational modelling & simulation* (CM&S) as well as regulatory science, for the benefit of patients. The simulations of SIMCor concern bench testing and preclinical and clinical assessment of medical devices. The exemplary use cases of ***transcatheter aortic valve implant* (TAVI) and *pulmonary artery pressure sensor* (PAPS)**, both cardiac medical devices, were chosen to evaluate the SIMCor methodology, but by no means the project intends to collect advice for a company-specific product.

A first round of regulatory stakeholders' consultation was already reported immediately after the first RAB meeting (M18) in *D2.5 - Regulatory feedback report (1)* (VPH, M19). The current document is meant to report on the second (M20-M39) round of consultations with regulators and the in-silico community at large. The first part of this document summarises the feedback obtained during the RAB meeting held in June 2023 and March 2024, while the second part reports other ongoing discussions with various regulatory authorities and standardisation offices.

Regulatory Advisory Board meetings

The Advisory Board

The advisory board is composed of experts from regulatory organisations, external to the consortium, who are at stake in the healthcare and medical device sector. The notified body TÜV SÜD was represented by Rene Bombien, and the FDA was represented by Brent Craven, both in the II RAB and III RAB meetings.

Name	Background and function	Organisation name	Organisation type
Rene Bombien	Cardiovascular surgeon. High-risk product assessor in regulatory processes for TÜV SÜD.	TÜV SÜD – Denmark MHS	Notified body
Brent Craven	Research scientist in computational modelling and medical devices. Senior Scientist & Program Manager (Acting), Credibility of Computational Modelling and Simulation Program, Office of Science & Engineering Laboratories. CDRH, FDA.	US FDA	National health regulatory authority

Table 1: Regulatory Advisory Board.

Methodology

The board members were invited to an online meeting on two separate occasions, **the II RAB meeting (20 June 2023)** and **the III RAB meeting (11 March 2024)**.

The agenda of both meetings included (1) an overview of SIMCor, (2) a presentation of the virtual cohort generation and validation methodology and results, (3) a presentation about the virtual device implantation and effect simulation (PAPS and TAVI) activity and (4) a presentation about the development of SOPs. The II RAB meeting also included an additional agenda item to discuss broad community-oriented open questions and a follow-up interaction on the socioeconomic impact assessment study.

The III RAB meeting started with the presentation of research results (virtual cohort generation and validation, modelling and simulation), followed by the presentation of SOP documents, and finally concluded with open discussions on the challenges of the in-silico modelling community. The detailed agenda, including the list of attendees, is available in **Appendix I (II RAB)** and **Appendix III (III RAB)**.

II RAB: scope and preliminary material

A few weeks before the II RAB meeting, several documents meant as preparation for the meeting were shared. This included general information on the project, as RAB members from the FDA and TÜV SÜD were not part of I RAB. Alongside this, the deliverables on SOPs, device implantation and effect simulation, virtual cohort generation and validation from M19-M30 were shared. These precisely included:

- *SIMCor one-page leaflet*¹, providing an overview of the project;
- *D4.1 - SOPs for data acquisition for in-silico models (UCL, M18)*, providing standards and workflow for preclinical and clinical data acquisition;
- *D4.2 - SOPs for data processing for in-silico models (CHA, M12)*, describing procedures and workflows for the processing of preclinical (in vitro, in vivo) and clinical data (imaging, sensor data) for generating virtual cohorts;
- *D4.4 - Guidelines for documentation (IIB, M12)*, providing guidelines for documentation of reports for hemodynamic studies of TAVI in medical device submissions;

¹ Rizzo, A., & Servidio, S. (2022). SIMCor. Leaflet. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6151181>.

- *D7.6 - Proof of principle of the complete virtual patient generator (TUE, M24)*, including the description of the first prototype of the virtual patient generator for TAVI;
- *D9.2 - Device-specific models (IIB, M24)*, reporting the joint device and vessel models for the different modalities;
- *D9.3 - Low-fidelity validation results (BIO, M30)* in its preliminary version, reporting low-fidelity validation results for TAVI and PAPS.

A list of questions was prepared by consortium partners to feed the discussion on the points of interest (**Appendix II**). However, as the presentations and discussions lasted longer than planned, the advisors agreed to attend a follow-up meeting dedicated to open questions (**Appendix II**) and discussions, as well as to participate in one-to-one interviews for the purpose of the socio-economic impact assessment.

III RAB: scope and preliminary material

A week before the III RAB meeting, the Board received the deliverables regarding the 3 **SOPs on in-silico analysis, validation and virtual cohort generation**, and more precisely:

- *D4.3 - SOPs for virtual cohort generation and validation (TUE, M36)*, describing procedures for optimal virtual cohort generation and validation.
- *D4.5 - SOPs for in-silico analysis of TAVI (IIB, M24)*, providing standard protocols for performing *computational fluid dynamics* (CFD) and *fluid-structure interaction* (FSI) simulations, as well as particle image velocimetry measurements of TAVI in medical device submissions.
- *D4.6 - SOPs for validation of in-silico models (BIO, M36)*, providing standard protocols for multi-level validation of in-silico models.

The meeting was meant to gather feedback on the progress since the previous RAB meeting, as well as collect specific reflections on the SOP documents. In addition, a few general open-ended questions were drafted along the lines of focus areas for in-silico trials.

RAB II: feedback

Notified body representative – Rene Bombien (TÜV SÜD, Denmark MHS)

Overall, the *notified body representative* (NBR) was impressed with the work. It is the feeling of the consortium that the NBR had the appropriate background to understand and properly appreciate the achievements, limitations and challenges of the work conducted in SIMCor.

Virtual cohort generation and validation

The NBR asked about the **type of parameters** that were considered, the **geometry of the valves** and other **physiological parameters** of the aortic root.

- The consortium clarified that the focus was on patients with moderate and severe stenosis and tricuspid aortic valves, as they are the most relevant for TAVI. However, the approach can also be extended to other types of parameters and pathologies, if appropriate data is available. There was a particular interest from the advisor for the capacity of the model to predict risks of adverse events.

In the MDR, *occurrence rates of adverse events in a given population* is of interest regarding the safety of a device (MDR Annex XIV part A).

- The consortium explained that it is not possible to assess all adverse events with this type of mechanistic model, but adverse events for PAPS were evaluated with a risk analysis.

Virtual device implantation and device effect simulation

The NBR pointed to the state of the art (MDR Art 61, and Annex I) that also consists of **non-straight-forward patients and other physiological characteristics** (e.g., no calcifications on the leaflets but in the annulus, the coronary ostia and the ascending aorta). The discussion also focused on the geometries used for the PAPS use case (e.g., pulmonary hypertension patients may have very thin and rigid pulmonary arteries).

- The consortium highlighted the difficulty of having access to data from specific subgroups of patients for the PAPS use case, such as heart failure patients (e.g., SIMCor has used tissue samples of the artery from 10 donors and healthy pigs). In principle, the high-fidelity model allows to account for every possible boundary condition and parameter but there is no indication to undergo a CT scan for pulmonary hypertension or *heart failure* (HF) patients. Therefore, data is only available for the patients who have HF as a comorbidity.

The NBR asked for the possibility of having models that can assess specific problems via in-silico, which allows manufacturers to avoid subsequent issues and thereby reduce stress on patients being part of clinical trials.

There is a requirement in the EU **Medical Device Regulation (MDR) 2017/745²** that the manufacturer should define the target population to place the device on the market and the specific risks that come with this target population. To this end, the question of interest for NBs was: “*What are the occurrence rates for the adverse effects in that given population?*”. These aspects should come into question when we propose using virtual populations, in particular when we estimate the risk that goes into ISO 14971³ (Medical devices — Application of risk management to medical devices).

- To this end, SIMCor started the risk analysis and identified the most critical adverse events.

The NBR from TÜV SÜD stressed that clinical assessments usually investigate the immediate effects and that those are quite well understood but **the information about the chronic use and prediction of mid- and long-term effects over 10 or 20 years are missing – in the MDR Annex I it is required that the benefit, safety and performance over the lifetime must be demonstrated: *this is where the unknown lies, at the moment.*** For the NBR, the implantation technique and short-term aspects are quite well understood already (e.g., paravalvular leakage). For what concerns reducing experiments, at the moment we are bound with the ISO-5840 (for heart valve prostheses), which prescribes sample sizes, but the real added value for *computational modelling and simulation* (CM&S) would be to provide extra data and estimate the behaviour of the device beyond those short-term aspects required in the MDR.

- SIMCor clarified that some of the endpoints that are addressed in the projects regard long-term performance (e.g., risk of migration, durability, thrombosis). However, modelling and simulation of mechanisms such as the remodelling of tissues, which is important for the risk of vessel wall perforation, is extremely difficult. A key effort of the consortium is to reflect on the way to calibrate the models with the observed clinical endpoints (e.g., for tissue remodelling measure peak contact stress and relate it to results obtained in mid/long term animal trials in terms of perforation event rate).

As required in the MDR Annex 15, clinical studies will include human patients, and it remained unclear to the NBR why no human data are used for the mapping of engineering metrics to clinical endpoints, instead of extrapolation from animal models, since bypassing the limitations of animal models is also why CM&S is important.

² Regulation - 2017/745 - EN - Medical Device Regulation - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)

³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/72704.html>

For regulatory translation, the NBR noted that some of the investigated endpoints were not aligned with those mentioned in existing standards (e.g., ISO 5840). The terms “efficacy” and “safety” are referred to as “performance and safety” in the MDR the concept of benefits for the patients is also key (c.f. MDR Art2- Definition 53)⁴. Looking at the benefit to the patient is as important as assessing the risk of adverse effects for medical devices.

Open questions - regulatory science

All parties recognised the importance of having this type of interaction between research/tech developers and regulatory stakeholders. The NBR advocates for interaction with H2020 or Horizon Europe projects as part of regulatory advisory boards, to inform themselves on the upcoming developments but also share their independent perspectives, agnostic of specific products or manufacturers.

Concerning the question on **statistics about applications received** and the related activities, several tools and resources were pointed out by the NBR such as the **EUDAMED platform**, or the list of regulatory opinions published under the *Clinical Evaluation Consultation Procedure* (CECP)⁵. In January 2023, the European Commission published its first annual report about medical devices subject to the CECP (Article 54) of the MDR.

The advisor indicated that, with the new **EUDAMED⁶ database, the transparency and public access to information about regulatory approval of medical devices is going to improve**. Information about adverse event rates and whatever comes in the post-market assessment should be available and might be relevant to fill in the in-silico models. Additionally, the following advisory from Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG), MDCG 2019-9 - Rev.1 - Summary of safety and clinical performance (SSCP)⁷- dt March 2022, was referred for further insights on clinical assessment reports.

Regulator representative – Brent Craven (FDA)

Virtual cohort generation and validation

The advisor wondered if the correlations between different parameters were considered and how combinations of parameters resulting in possible non-realistic anatomies were treated.

- The strategy explored by the consortium is indeed to consider correlations and to use both the data-driven filtering to identify non-observed combinations (already implemented) and the functional outcome-based filtering to better identify non-physiologic virtual patients.

The discussion also focused on the choice of boundary conditions and material parameters to reflect the variety of patients, e.g., ‘severe to moderate stenosis’.

- The consortium explained that generic tissue properties and steady hemodynamic boundary conditions are considered to compare pressure drops with the CFD simulations, at the moment. However, the objective is to move towards FSI simulations, taking into account calcifications to be rigid, as compared to the tissue, for example.

Virtual device implantation and device effect simulation

The advisor opened the discussion on the computational cost of the high-fidelity simulations, the possibility of using *high-performance computing* (HPC), and the risk of loss of accuracy when moving to low-fidelity models.

- The consortium acknowledged that high-fidelity simulations, particularly full-FSI simulations, were quite expensive, but they were needed only for very selected problems. Although using

⁴ Regulation - 2017/745 - EN - Medical Device Regulation - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)

⁵ https://health.ec.europa.eu/medical-devices-expert-panels/experts/list-opinions-provided-under-cecp_en

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/tools/eudamed/#/screen/home>

⁷ https://health.ec.europa.eu/document/download/5f082b2f-8d51-495c-9ab9-985a9f39ece4_en

HPC is possible, it poses licence issues, at the moment. The calculation time of the entire FSI, for opening and closing of the heart valve, takes about 4 days on a local 16-core workstation. However, this is not possible for all geometries, as the mechanical properties have a huge impact on the computational cost. On that matter, the consortium has been describing the type of models to use for each problem/application (e.g., high fidelity FSI model for studying the interactions between fixation and vessels or reduced order model for questions related to flow displacement).

The advisor was interested in knowing how the model could inform long-term clinical outcomes (e.g., mortality, hospitalisation), which are important endpoints for the clinical trials.

- The consortium presented the difficulty of linking the parameters of the model to these types of clinical outcomes and described the envisioned approach.

Open questions - regulatory science

The advisor acknowledged that the development of the *American Society of Mechanical Engineers* (ASME) V&V 40 “Assessing credibility of computational modelling through verification and validation: application to medical devices”⁸ has made a tremendous difference in the field since, prior to that standard, the expectations and way of reporting CM&S were highly inconsistent.

The advisor recognises that validation (especially clinical validation) is a major challenge for the modelling community, especially when it comes to clinical data (how to obtain, how to validate them, etc.). In addition, the advisor from the FDA made brief observations during open questions at the end of the II RAB meeting.

- **About benchmark dataset:** FDA’s Centre for Devices and Radiological Health (CDRH) researchers have developed several benchmark datasets that are publicly available and can be used for validation. However, none of the datasets are for clinical validation.
- **About subjectivity while determining the risk of the model and required level of validation:** In addition to ASME V&V40⁹, the U.S. FDA has issued the guidance “Assessing the credibility of computational modelling and simulation in medical submissions”¹⁰ that offers additional clarity and options for model credibility evidence. FDA encourages the community to consider a Q-submission to bring such discussions.
- **Comments on the FDA guidance document**¹¹ are well received and factored into the major revisions.
- **View on community-based efforts towards standardisation of modelling:** for instance, drafting the standard operating procedures and best practices as in SIMCor contributes towards examples for ASME V&V40 and FDA guidance. We need consistency and examples of how to do this, to that end SIMCor SOPs are valuable.

⁸ V&V 40, A. S. M. E. (2018). Assessing credibility of computational modeling through verification and validation: application to medical devices. *The American Society of Mechanical Engineers*.

⁹ V&V 40, A. S. M. E. (2018). Assessing credibility of computational modeling through verification and validation: application to medical devices. *The American Society of Mechanical Engineers*.

¹⁰ Guidance for Industry and Food and Drug Administration Staff; Docket Number: FDA-2021-D-0980; Link: <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/assessing-credibility-computational-modeling-and-simulation-medical-device-submissions>

¹¹ Guidance for Industry and Food and Drug Administration Staff; Docket Number: FDA-2021-D-0980; Link: <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/assessing-credibility-computational-modeling-and-simulation-medical-device-submissions>

Outlook and conclusions

The following pointers seemed of particular importance and for which efforts should be allocated:

- **Ensuring the representativity of a clinically relevant variety of patients**, to improve the potential impact and transfer of such technology.
- **The use of appropriate geometries and physical parameter values for specific patient groups** observed in the clinic was a major recommendation.

These would be needed to bring the computational models closer to the real-life context of use.

Additionally, clearer **mechanisms (e.g., FDA Q-submission) are in place for manufacturers to open the dialogue with regulators** and request advice on specific applications (e.g., mock submissions) in the US market than in the European area.

Finally, the **regulatory advisory board sees the added value of the in-silico approach** to solve the limitations of current traditional methods, in particular for predicting acute quantities of interest. Nevertheless, modellers acknowledge that **predicting long-term clinical outcomes was also one of the biggest challenges for in-silico mechanistic models.**

III RAB: feedback

Virtual cohort generation

The consortium presented the **virtual cohort generator** developed in SIMCor, with due insights on the underlying sampling strategy, the relevant filtering approach (data-driven vs clinically plausible) and the three-level validation framework.

(1) Baseline cohort sample size and parameterization challenges (Brent Craven - FDA)

The FDA advisor opened the discussion by inquiring about the number of baseline subjects from which the parameters were extracted, i.e., the baseline sample size to generate the virtual cohorts of stenotic aortic valve geometries. Also, clarification was sought on any associated challenges in fitting 33 dimensional parameter space, with the baseline sample size.

- The consortium WP7 leader acknowledged the significance of the question and walked through the details on the base sample (N=97) and highlighted the reasons and possible gaps for future work. Briefly, the target for base population size was set to 100 samples, based on the data from CHA, with additional samples from UCL and TUE, set aside for cross-validation. However, owing to data quality, the final number of samples used in the current virtual cohort generator remained at 97 subjects. Though the input geometry is fairly well captured from this sample population, it was acknowledged that parameter space remains sparse. This would likely be the case, owing to challenges associated with data provenance, anonymisation, etc. Moreover, if the model is to be applied by other context-of-use (e.g., bi-leaflet valves), the entire parameter space needs to be recalibrated with due representation of relevant additional samples.

(2) Filtering strategy for realistic virtual patients (Brent Craven - FDA)

The exchanges on sample size led to questions on the filtering strategy adopted by SIMCor and possible reasons for not attaining physiological responses in some virtual patients.

- The team highlighted that this was very much expected, given the limited sample parameter space and boundary conditions. Therefore, the consortium devised multiple filters, as a strategy to cope with these non-realistic virtual patients. The consortium clarified that several filters can be devised, ranging from demographic (e.g., female) to clinical criteria, like pressure drops, that reflect clinically plausible physiological responses. At the same time, the team

emphasised that the chosen parameters and boundary conditions need to go through the rigorous three-tier validation strategy – self-validation, patient-level validation, and cross-validation scheme. The need for relevant validation data was stressed.

(3) Baseline cohort sample size and recommendations of ISO 5840 (Rene Bombien - TÜV SÜD, Denmark MHS)

Building on the above exchanges of baseline cohort, **the representative from the notified body** raised a critical question on the number of samples (=150) recommended by ISO 5840, for heart valve prostheses. Given that this is the standard accepted for clinical investigation, it was asked why there was a deviation from this standard. Thus, it was suggested that we should formulate another validation layer for the proposed virtual cohort generator model.

- Regarding the sample size and the adherence to the standard, the consortium reflected that data quality-related challenges led us to settle for 97 baseline samples. Moreover, the strategy of the consortium was to generate much higher sample sizes for the in-silico trial framework, by leveraging our virtual cohort generator. Also, ongoing efforts to include additional data from UCL and TUE for cross-validation were highlighted.
- Independent of the above reflections, the consortium thanked the advisor for this valuable reference listed in the ISO standard. The consortium was open to considering the specifics associated with ISO 5840, in its validation strategy.

Virtual device implantation and device effect simulation

The consortium member IIB presented the latest results on TAVI device implantation and device effect simulation, based on the virtual cohort generated by TUE, whereby the clinical endpoint of TAVI-related thrombosis and paravalvular leakage were investigated. Likewise, BIO presented the use of low-fidelity validation (in vitro, ex vivo, in vivo) for the prediction of engineering metrics and high-fidelity validation (only in vivo) for clinical endpoints (perforation, migration, thrombosis), with specific emphasis on the PAPS device.

Following the presentations on in-silico clinical trials for TAVI and validation experiments mapping engineering metrics with clinical endpoints for PAPS, the FDA advisor had three critical questions for the consortium, as below.

(1) Clinical endpoint for thrombosis based on surrogate velocity metrics (Brent Craven - FDA)

The advisor from the FDA observed that the clinical endpoint for TAVI related to thrombosis is measured on velocity-based surrogate metrics, rather than the actual thrombosis measures like platelet activation.

- IIB acknowledged the observation and outlined the challenges and rationale behind the approach. Given that thrombosis is a complex phenomenon that occurs at different time points and spatial scales, the necessary experimental setup with blood constitutes a challenging process to validate thrombosis. Therefore, the strategy was to use velocity-based hemodynamic parameters correlated to thrombosis, as these can be at least validated using in-vitro measurements. In other words, the use of surrogate metrics helps limit the eventuality of not achieving validation at all. Nevertheless, additional effort was made to not just limit to experimental results, but also simulate numerical results in parallel and correlate.

(2) Durability testing beyond force tests (Brent Craven - FDA)

To evaluate the durability of the valve, the FDA advisor emphasised the need to go beyond applying forces, to test strain on the valve.

- To this, the researcher clarified that not only radial forces were used but also other forces on the valve attachment, alongside conducting fatigue tests. Similar to the thrombosis endpoint, the strategy was to identify mechanical properties that allow prediction of the occurrence of adverse events, rather than aiming for a patient-specific occurrence prediction. This relates to the rupture of the stent or the endpoint of the stent fracture, as its occurrence is very rare. For instance, no report on the occurrence of stent fracture in either the UCL or CHA cohort was noted.

(3) Scope of in-silico clinical trial to cover all clinical endpoints (Brent Craven - FDA)

An important discussion was triggered by the FDA advisor on whether the consortium refers to in-silico clinical trials as one aimed at reducing the sample size of clinical or animal trials. If so, then the proposed in-silico methods and validation schemes must accommodate all clinical endpoints that would normally be addressed in a real clinical trial. For instance, the endpoint of electrical conduction problems after implantation is not addressed in the current in-silico clinical trial. Given the above reasons, the consortium was cautioned that if the above aspects are not addressed, the statistical power of the trial will be lower.

- The consortium clarified that the mission of SIMCor was not to realise a full-blown in-silico clinical trial or a clinical trial, given the limited resources and time scale of the project. Rather, the objective was to use modelling and simulation to answer specific clinical endpoints and certainly not all of them. Likewise, there are several models, which independently target a specific clinical endpoint. In other words, a conscious choice was made among the available models for each endpoint. In addition, the following observations were made:
 - To assess multiple endpoints in a collective manner, different models must be combined. However, a combined model might be prohibitive for resources, parameterisation, etc. Hence, the strategy was to focus on one clinical endpoint at a time.
 - The consortium has developed the capacity to assess all clinical endpoints, including conduction, at least for TAVI investigation. For PAPS, this is still not the case, hence the possibility to reduce the number of human samples is lowered at this moment.
 - Finally, it was noted that the in-silico trials envisaged by the consortium were also targeting the insights and feedback for device development, rather than clinical trials in a regulatory approval process.

Standard operating procedures

Following the presentation of research results, the consortium briefly presented the overarching scheme of SOP documents drafted for the entire in-silico workflow. This was followed by a walk-through of the three SOP documents realised in the second reporting period. Subsequently, feedback on their relevance and usability in the in-silico development and regulatory process was solicited.

Brent Craven – FDA

The advisor from the FDA commented that SOPs are a good initiative. The value of such documents was seen as a way to illustrate the approach, risk assessment pathway and means to explain how ASME V&V40 and FDA guidance documents were followed.

On the above note, the consortium was encouraged to publicly share the SOP work as the community needs examples of how ASME V&V40 and FDA guidance documents are used in practice. Also, the FDA is interested in potential collaborations in this area and is open to considering joint publications in the context of facilitating the wider uptake by the community.

Rene Bombien - TÜV SÜD

The representative from the NB echoed and agreed with the observations of the FDA representative.

Open discussion on common challenges

At the end of presentations, questions and exchanges, the advisors and the consortium members organically progressed into open discussions.

*Theme 1: assessing uncertainty***Rene Bombien - TÜV SÜD**

The consortium was asked to comment on “How to assess the uncertainties noted by the consortium?”

- The consortium reflected that this has not been easy, but an effort has been made to reason and explain our approaches through documents like SOPs. Likewise, bridging from animal experiments to clinical endpoints, or modelling thrombosis, were acknowledged to be challenging problems. Further, fundamental research on thrombosis modelling is ongoing, where the focus is to be close to clinical applications.
- Consortium members highlighted that standardisation and recycling the context of use (CoU) and validated models seem quite challenging for the community. For big players and non-cardio domains, this seems possible.

Brent Craven – FDA

In response to the above observations from the consortium, the advisor from the FDA echoed the following sentiments, by appreciating that the consortium identified many questions and challenges that the medical device community struggles with.

The FDA advisor clarified that the problems of standardisation and model reuse are not just for this sub-domain of cardiovascular devices, but rather one for the medical device industry broadly (e.g., unlike the aviation or automotive industries). He further emphasised the need to work together as a community to overcome standardisation challenges.

Theme 2: replacing clinical trials

- Considering that replacing clinical trials and covering all clinical endpoints remains a challenge for the in-silico community, the consortium sought perspectives on how to formulate in-silico trials to reduce the effort on real-world studies, be it best practices, suggestions, or recommendations on how to simplify real-world approval within in-silico studies.

Brent Craven – FDA

The advisor from the FDA carefully rephrased the question as follows: “How can in-silico methods be useful?” and shared his broad thoughts. Replacing patients in a clinical study is challenging for in-silico trials. This requires that the statistical power of a trial is not lowered, and all clinical endpoints are captured. Considering the challenges for modelling and simulation studies concerning replacing patients, there is the additional possibility of using in-silico evidence to “enrich” a clinical trial. In this case, the number of subjects is not reduced, but rather modelling is used to inform inclusion criteria and de-risk the trial. Also, the use of modelling for the design process by manufacturers was noted as a potentially impactful use of in-silico evidence.

*Theme 3: modelling challenges***Brent Craven - FDA**

Building on the flow of the discussions, the FDA advisor asked the consortium to reflect on the biggest challenges that the modellers struggle with.

Following is the summary of key observations made by consortium members.

Response of the consortium

- Mapping of engineering metrics and clinical outcomes.
- Lack of standardisation in data acquisition, and often the data required for model parameterisation and or validation is not available from clinical routine (i.e., real-world data).
- Need to include the risk factors/prognostic factors to be incorporated into the model design.
- Need for calibrated and validated models.
 - For well-established models, event rates are low, making validation difficult. For novel models, animal sample sizes are small, which often provides limited data for calibration. If we calculate the sample size, we have to take into account that sample size is efficacy driven. It is good for patients and manufacturers to reduce adverse events, but we cannot reduce the efficacy of the device.
- The uncertainty makes it very difficult to quantify the socioeconomic impact assessment of in-silico trials.
- Paradigms of in-silico trials and clinical trials seem too different to merge for the current regulatory approval process.

Outlook and conclusions

Reflecting on the various exchanges and observations from the consortium, the advisors shared their perspectives that overarchingly summarise the current state and needs of the hour, for future in-silico endeavours.

Rene Bombien - TÜV SÜD

The advisor acknowledged the reservations of modellers in attempting to substitute conventional clinical trials through modelling and simulation approaches. Nevertheless, it was stressed that conventional clinical investigations might be supported by a relook into the whole process. He reflected on his field experience that the clinical investigations may also not always be ideal, as it stands. There remain gaps and unanswered questions, which run the risk of sub-optimal study designs and outcomes. For instance, gaps include:

- Ever increasing need for patient collection for clinical trials. This is possibly not sustainable in the long run.
- The current setup does not have the necessary tools to optimally define inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- There are gaps between the actual regulations and hard reality when it comes to patient collection.

Emphasis was made on where in-silico can make significant contributions. For instance, opportunities include:

- Sample size of data collection: using computer modelling and simulation to answer, 'How many patients are enough to ascertain safety and efficacy?' This can help cut down variability.
- Measure of patient benefit: it is difficult to estimate, but important because what all actors strive for is the ultimate benefit of patients.

A passionate call was made not to be deterred by the overwhelming expectations, but rather to leverage the potential of in-silico technologies to unravel the current black box, for bringing home the real benefit to patients. An encouraging message to modellers was relayed: *'Even if in-silico cannot foot the entire validation cycle as that of a conventional clinical trial, we must strive to explore for the betterment of patients.'*

Brent Craven - FDA

Listening to the reflection of the consortium and the exchanges with the advisor from TÜV SÜD, the FDA representative had two key take-home messages. First, in addition to sample size, correlation between engineering quantities and clinical quantities is a key challenge and critical focus area for the community.

Further, the FDA advisor expressed the following outlook on clinical trials and computational modelling and simulation: clinical trials are the gold standard and, as such, are widely accepted by a large group of stakeholders, and have been so for a long time. It is not trivial for them to switch and accept alternative evidence. It will, thus, be important to validate modelling and simulation by comparing them with clinical trials to provide information that CM&S evidence is as reliable as clinical trials for the wider community. Hence, a sense of caution was advocated so that a wrong step does not hamper the entire community.

Other regulatory stakeholder consultations

Besides the feedback gathered during RAB meetings, various other institutions at stake in the regulatory process of new therapies were consulted during M31-M39. This was necessary to reflect on how to advance computational modelling and simulations for health technology product development and assess expectations, interests, needs and requirements. The following sub-sections presents an overview of such initiatives where consortium members participated in *task forces* (TFs) and workshops, as well as attended events themed around regulatory aspects of in-silico technologies.

Avicenna Alliance TFs

Notified bodies TF

VPH is a representative of the Avicenna Alliance Notified Bodies TF. This allowed us to follow through with the latest developments and evolving landscape within the standardisation and conformity assessment bodies.

Good Simulation Practice TF and book

Consortium members actively participated in the definition of *good simulation practice* (GSP) as part of the InSilicoWorld *Community of Practice* (CoP). The consortium also contributed to multiple chapters of the book on **Towards Good Simulation Practice (GSP)**¹², which has now taken the shape of an open-source publication playing a crucial role in building standards towards GSP, thus forming a basis for initiating discussions with regulators (i.e., FDA) on necessary standards and guidelines for CM&S through the GSP TF of the Avicenna Alliance.

Liaison with standard organisations

International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) Technical Committee

VPH champions the In-silico community of practice, which includes renowned in-silico experts, organisations, and Horizon projects. Together with the Avicenna Alliance, VPH was instrumental in getting the voice of the modelling community to the IEC TC. Thanks to the continued efforts of various collaborators, the **Avicenna Alliance joined the IEC TC 62 Medical Equipment, software and systems**¹³ **and ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology**¹⁴ / **WG 5 committee** in December 2023. Of note, efforts were made through these channels to set up the possibility of **developing an IEC-ISO equivalent to the ASME V&V40**, which could eventually lead to harmonising the standards in the CE marking system. It will be a long journey, but a critical milestone that the modelling community is set to team up for.

Workshops, seminars and panel discussions

Manifesto for the Promotion of Digital Modelling and Simulation (M&S) in France

Lessons learnt and regulatory challenges emerging from SIMCor were echoed by VPH at the **Avicenna Alliance, NAFEM and MICADO seminar** for the launch of the **Manifesto for the Promotion of Digital Modeling and Simulation (M&S) in France (13 June 2023)**. The session included roundtable discussions with industry and regulatory bodies to evaluate challenges and necessary initiatives to advance the consideration of in-silico evidence as part of the regulatory evaluation process.

¹² Viceconti, Marco, and Luca Emili. "Toward Good Simulation Practice: Best Practices for the Use of Computational Modelling and Simulation in the Regulatory Process of Biomedical Products." (2024): 144.

¹³ https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1245,25

¹⁴ <https://www.iso.org/committee/4514241.html>

Digital Twin for Health DT4H.BE

The consortium also participated in the **Digital Twin for Health DT4H.BE (Leuven, 29 September 2023)**, the first meeting of the Belgian Ecosystem on Digital Twins, supported by the *Belgium Federal Agency on Policy and Support* (BO SA), where VPH yielded an open engagement with regulatory bodies, on the sidelines of a **panel discussion that included actors from industry, trade bodies, academia, regulators, and policymakers**. The panel converged on the need for open and constructive exchanges between in-silico technology developers and regulatory bodies. A European Commission representative attending the event took note of the **misalignments and barriers that regulators, academia, and industry face**, while acknowledging the request for health sector-specific engagement for policy development.

Avicenna Days

Participation in the 3-day annual **Avicenna Days¹⁵ (10-13 October, 2023)**, which brought together regulators, scientists, researchers, industry, and academia leaders to update the healthcare community on recent progress and achievements related to the **adoption and deployment of in-silico methods**.

Ecosystem of Digital Twins in Healthcare (EDITH) open meetings and consultation activities

Participation in the public consultation and community events (January 2024) related to the **'Roadmap on building the virtual human twin¹⁶**, championed by the *Ecosystem of Digital Twins in Healthcare (EDITH) coordination and support action¹⁷ and the **Manifesto on the Virtual Human Twins (VHT)¹⁸**, a flagship initiative of the European Commission to support science and technology developments required for building advanced VHT-based solutions in healthcare.*

InSilicoWorld workshop "The regulator barriers to in-silico trials"

CHA, BIO, and VPH participated in the cross-project workshop to mutually learn and contribute to the community efforts, in advancing the current state of affairs on in-silico trials. Learning and discussions included exchanges with ASME V&V40 committee members and those from the FDA, which eventually contributed back to the understanding of regulatory barriers for the consortium.

FDA/MDIC Symposium on Computational Modelling and Simulation (CM&S)

The symposium convened in Washington DC on 16-17 April 2024. CHA and VPH took part in the symposium, which brought together Innovations in CM&S for developing in-silico evidence for regulatory approval. It also gave a valuable opportunity to liaise with regulators from the U.S. and Europe, during panel discussions. More importantly, it was not only an opportunity to echo the barriers from the perspective of technology developers but also learn about the challenges from the regulators' perspective.

¹⁵ <https://www.avicenna-alliance.com/avicenna-days/avicenna-days-aad-2023.html?tab=about>

¹⁶ M. Viceconti, M. De Vos, S. Mellone and L. Geris, "Position Paper From the Digital Twins in Healthcare to the Virtual Human Twin: A Moon-Shot Project for Digital Health Research," in *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 491-501, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2023.3323688.

¹⁷ <https://www.edith-csa.eu/>; see EDITH Roadmap Section 4.4.1

¹⁸ www.virtualhumantwins.eu/

Conclusion and outlook

The consortium has been proactive in engaging with stakeholders from the regulatory and standardisation spectrum. To this end, SIMCor followed a multipronged strategy, which included annual **RAB meetings**, but also a continuous **community outreach and engagement activity** in conferences, workshops, panel discussions and community events, specifically **themed around regulatory discussions**. Looking back at this approach, we can reflect that these complementary interactions, both within the project and with the community at large, were instrumental for SIMCor to understand and contribute to the regulatory science surrounding in-silico methods. Such a balanced engagement helped SIMCor establish a measured, yet open engagement with regulators, who are often constrained by their time and code of conduct.

This was achieved by leveraging the research and innovation results on in-silico methods for implantable device development and validation of consortium partners. Such results were key for the regulators to take interest in the upcoming advancements. Further, **regulatory advisors endorsed** that the engagements with **SIMCor offered opportunities to mutually learn and share valuable perspectives** with the in-silico technology development community. As for the consortium, the **RAB forum facilitated the much-needed external feedback** to advance in-silico technologies as part of the regulatory process, thus meeting objectives 1 and 4 set out at the start of the project.

Regulatory consultations with key stakeholders, namely *standardisation bodies*, *regulatory agencies*, *conformity assessment bodies* and the *in-silico technology developers* revealed many gaps, challenges and questions. The common ground was establishing a pathway for the credibility assessment of in-silico methods that ultimately yield safe access to medical innovation for patients. To this end, **synergies need to be harnessed to make a collective effort to establish standards, by proactively participating and contributing towards community initiatives**. These include responding to public consultations on standardisation/guidance, participation in working groups that establish standards and, more importantly, championing the learnings and best practices from research projects to the wider community.

Consortium partners continue to engage in community initiatives like public consultations of the FDA, as well as aligning with European initiatives, e.g., the EDITH-CSA¹⁹, that advocates for FAIR-sharing collection of standards²⁰ for the modelling community. Further, through project outcomes, SIMCor continues to play an active role by drafting **SOPs**, opening up project results to the public domain and **sharing learnings from interactions with regulatory agencies** as public deliverables.

¹⁹ <https://www.edith-csa.eu/>;

²⁰ <https://fairsharing.org/4787>;

Appendix

Appendix I – II RAB agenda

II RAB

20 June 2023, 15:00 - 17:00 CEST

Meeting agenda and participants

Participants

Advisory board members	Brent Craven, <i>Food and Drug Association</i> Rene Bombien, <i>TÜV SÜD</i>
Consortium members	Jan Brüning, <i>Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin (CHA)</i> , Anna Rizzo, <i>Lynkeus (LYN)</i> , Andreas Arndt, <i>Biotronik (BIO)</i> , Pablo Verde, <i>European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN)</i> , Miriam Reiss, <i>Institut für Höhere Studien – Institute for Advanced Studies (IHS)</i> , Michael Stiehm, Finja Borowski, Jan Oldenburg <i>Institut für ImplantatTechnologie und Biomaterialien e.V. (IIB)</i> , Wouter Huberts, <i>Technische Universität Eindhoven (TUE)</i> , Claudio Capelli, <i>University College of London (UCL)</i> , Liesbet Geris, <i>Raphaëlle Lesage, Virtual Physiological Human Institute (VPH)</i>

Agenda

Time	Details	Lead
15:00 – 15:10	Greetings and introduction	Jan Brüning (CHA) Anna Rizzo (LYN)
15:10 - 15:20	SIMCor: overview Overview of project mission and objectives, summary of the first reporting period activity	
15:20 – 15:30	Virtual cohort generation and validation for aortic valve disease: overview and latest results	Wouter Huberts (TUE)
15:30 – 15:50	Virtual device implantation and effect simulation for TAVI and PAPS: overview and latest results	Michael Stiehm (IIB) Andreas Arndt (BIO)
15:50 – 16:00	Definition of standard operating procedures for in-silico trials in cardiology.	Raphaëlle Lesage, Liesbet Geris (VPH)
16:00 - 16:10	Assessment of socioeconomic impacts of in-silico technologies	Miriam Reiss, IHS
16:10 – 17:00	Q&A session & Final wrap-up	Raphaëlle Lesage (VPH) Jan Brüning (CHA) Anna Rizzo (LYN)

Appendix II – Preparatory questions for the II RAB meeting

- How has the assessment of in-silico trial results evolved in the last years in the US/ in Europe, in your view?
- What is often missing in the submission of CM&S results? What would you expect to see more often?
- Is the concept of « virtual population » frequently proposed in regulatory submissions, is the term mentioned as such?
- We see the translation of engineering output into clinical outcome as a challenge, what is the view of regulators on that point? Are any solutions recommended?
- What in your view is the main break to the uptake of this type of technology?
- How to improve engagement and communication with regulatory, standardisation and notified bodies?
- Are you aware of any Research projects in which regulators are direct partners/contributors?
- About mock submission at FDA. Are you aware of any equivalent mechanisms to interact with regulators and request advice, in Europe?
- Do you think that your organization has the appropriate workforce to evaluate applications with CM&S data/ with in-silico trials/Artificial Intelligence models? In terms of skills and the number of resources?
- How is continuous training of employees managed within NBs? At FDA?
- The National Cancer Institute (NCI) Community Hub initiated and published valuable CFD validation benchmarks (benchmark nozzle and blood pump, https://ncihub.org/wiki/FDA_CFD). Are there any other benchmarks planned, for example, a benchmark which covers the pulsatile condition of the cardiovascular system? Can we make suggestions for further benchmark cases, if yes, how and to whom can we do this?
- Real-world data: Is the use of real-world data, e.g., for validation, something that is being considered and done? What are the challenges, or needs?
- There are various documents in which the assessment of the model risk is an essential part of the process (FDA draft guidance, V&V40, NASA Technical Handbook NASA-HDBK-7009A). How can we connect the risk of a model and the required V&V activities? Is there any guidance for it?
- In Europe, we don't have an overarching standard like the ASME VV40. Do you think that field-specific standards are sufficient and should simply be refined or do you see a role for overarching/harmonised standards equivalent to the US ASME V&V 40?
- Handover of EC's experts to EMA. What will be the impact on the activity of European NBs? Could this have any positive or negative influence on the capacity of manufacturers to submit in-silico data?
- FDA draft guidance (Dec 2021): SIMCor submitted a feedback letter during the public call. Are you aware of any updates or future developments?

Feedback on the above questions were thematically grouped and summarised under the section 'RAB II: feedback' - 'open questions – regulatory science' of this report. Owing to confidentiality and/or code-of-conduct reasons, few topics could not be discussed and/or reported.

Appendix III – III RAB agenda

III RAB

11 March 2024, 15:00 - 17:00 CEST

Meeting agenda and participants**Participants**

Advisory board members	Brent Craven, <i>Food and Drug Association</i> Rene Bombien, <i>TÜV SÜD</i>
Consortium members	Jan Brüning, <i>Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin (CHA)</i> , Anna Rizzo, <i>Lynkeus (LYN)</i> , Andreas Arndt, <i>Biotronik (BIO)</i> , Sigfried Eisenberg, <i>Institute for Advanced Studies (IHS)</i> , Michael Stiehm, Finja Borowski, <i>Institut für ImplantatTechnologie und Biomaterialien e.V. (IIB)</i> , Wouter Huberts, <i>Technische Universität Eindhoven (TUE)</i> , Malte Rolf-Pissarczyk (TUG); Silvia Schievano, <i>University College of London (UCL)</i> ; Christian Ohmann (ECRIN) Liesbet Geris, Janaki Raman Rangarajan, <i>Virtual Physiological Human Institute (VPH)</i>

Agenda

Time	Details	Lead
15:00 – 15:20	Greetings and introduction	Anna Rizzo (LYN)
15:10 - 15:20	SIMCor: overview	
15:20 – 15:30	Virtual cohort generation and validation for aortic valve disease: overview and latest results	Wouter Huberts (TUE)
15:30 – 15:50	Virtual device implantation and effect simulation for TAVI and PAPS: overview and latest results	Michael Stiehm (IIB) Jan Romberg (BIO) Andreas Arndt (BIO)
15:50 – 16:00	Definition of standard operating procedures for in-silico trials in cardiology.	Janaki Raman Rangarajan, Liesbet Geris (VPH), Michael Stiehm Jan Romberg Jan Brüning
16:00 - 16:10	Q submission to the FDA for the PAPS use case: lessons learnt and open questions	Jan Romberg Janaki Raman Rangarajan
16:10 – 17:00	Q&A session & Final wrap-up	Janaki Raman Rangarajan (VPH), Jan Brüning (CHA) Anna Rizzo (LYN)